

Synthesis and Pharmacology of 1-(4-Aryl-1-Piperazinyl-alkyl)-4-(4-Methoxyphenyl) Piperidine-2,6-Diones : Tranquilizers

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Manuscript received 11 December 1979, revised 8 January 1981, accepted 23 April 1981

1-(4-Aryl-1-piperazinylethyl/propyl)-4-(4-methoxyphenyl) piperidine-2,6-diones were prepared by condensing 1-(ω -aminoalkyl)-4-arylpiperazines with 3-(4-methoxyphenyl) pentane dioic anhydride in dry pyridine. These compounds showed mild CNS depressant action. Their antagonism of increased toxicity of amphetamine in mice was recorded.

In an effort to synthesize non-phenothiazine type psychosedative agents, new classes of compounds have been developed. Despite immense search with this objective, the last word is yet far off. An acceptable psychosedative must exert selective depression of psychic functions rather than producing non-specific sedation.

N-(Substitutedaminoalkyl)glutarimides (I) possess CNS depressant action¹⁻⁴. It has been discovered that substitution on the glutarimide skeleton markedly influences the pharmacological actions of these compounds⁵. Recent reports on N-(piperazinylalkyl) glutarimides possessing promising psychosedative action are intriguing⁶⁻⁸. The presence of 4-phenyl-1-piperazinylalkyl group in the total structure is essential for the biological effect in a series of closely related compounds⁶. 4-(4-Alkoxyphenyl) glutarimides are known to possess significant CNS depressant action⁹. We, therefore, envisaged the synthesis of 1-[ω -(4-aryl-1-piperazinyl)-alkyl]-4-(4-methoxyphenyl) piperidine-2,6-diones (IX and X).

1-Arylpiperazines (IV) were prepared according to the Pollard's method¹⁰. N-[2-(4-Aryl-1-piperazinyl) ethyl] phthalimides(II)¹¹ were hydrolysed by 20% HCl (the Gabriel's method) to give 1-(2-aminoethyl)-4-arylpiperazines (III). III were condensed with 3-(4-methoxyphenyl) glutaric anhydride¹²(VIII) in dry pyridine to obtain IX. IR spectrum of IX_a (KBr) showed peaks at 1664 and 1727 (-CO-N-CO-); PMR of IX_d (CDCl₃): 2.23 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.63 [6H, m, -CH₂-N(CH₂-)₂], 2.83 (5H, m, -CO-CH₂-CH-CH₂-CO-), 3.07 [4H, t, Ar-N(CH₂-)₂], 3.73 (3H, s,

Ar-OCH₃) and 3.93 (2H, t, (-CO)₂N-CH₂). 1-Arylpiperazines (IV) were added across the double bond in acrylonitrile (V) to get 1-(2-cyanoethyl)-4-arylpiperazines (VI). IR of VI_a (KBr): 2225 (-C≡N). VI were reduced by catalytic reduction¹³ to 1-(3-aminopropyl)-4-arylpiperazines (VII). VII were condensed with VIII in dry pyridine to furnish X. IR of X_g (KBr): 1660 and 1716 (-CO-N-CO-); PMR of X_g (CDCl₃): 1.75 (2H, m, -CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-), 2.5 [6H, m, -CH₂-N(CH₂-)₂], 2.8 (5H, m, -CO-CH₂-CH-CH₂-CO-), 3.1 [4H, t, Ar-N(CH₂-)₂], 3.73 (3H, s, Ar-OCH₃) and 3.8 [2H, t, (-CO)₂N-CH₂-].

TABLE 1—1-[ω-(4-ARYL-1-PIPERAZINYL)ALKYL]-4-(4-METHOXYPHENYL) PIPERIDINE-2,6-DIONE (IX and X)

Compd	R	n	Yield* %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	N analysis**		Amphetamine antagonis*** ED ₅₀ mg/k
						Found	Calcd.	
IXa	H	2	30	174-75	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄	10.35	10.31	38
IXb	2-CH ₃	2	24	182-83	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₄	9.91	9.97	24
IXc	3-CH ₃	2	41	150-51	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₄	9.92	9.97	60
IXd	4-OH	2	36	179-80	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₅	10.08	9.97	53
IXe	2-Cl	2	25	158-59	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₄	9.55	9.51	28
IXf	3-Cl	2	39	186-87	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₄	9.47	9.51	43
IXg	4-Cl	2	36	167-68	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ ClN ₄ O ₄	9.57	9.51	34
Xa	H	3	55	164-65	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₄	9.99	9.97	21
Xb	2-CH ₃	3	51	97-98	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄	9.71	9.68	18
Xc	3-OH	3	56	117-18	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₅	9.61	9.65	37
Xd	4-CH ₃	3	54	106-07	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄	9.62	9.65	42
Xe	2-Cl	3	46	101-02	C ₂₅ H ₂₇ ClN ₄ O ₄	9.28	9.22	10.5
Xf	3-Cl	3	60	111-12	C ₂₅ H ₂₇ ClN ₄ O ₄	9.18	9.22	35
Xg	4-Cl	3	63	188-89	C ₂₅ H ₂₇ ClN ₄ O ₄	9.17	9.22	30

* Yield based on the weight of the anhydride (VIII)

** All the compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

*** ED₅₀: Dose required to protect 50% of the animals from the LD₅₀ dose of amphetamine sulphate (subcutaneous).

Experimental

All the melting points reported are uncorrected. IR spectra were run on a Beckmann Acculab-10 infrared spectrophotometer (ν in cm^{-1}). Pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian-60 instrument (60 MHz) and the values were in δ units (ppm) with TMS as the internal reference.

1-(2-Aminoethyl)-4-phenylpiperazines (IIIa): N-[2-(4-Phenyl-1-piperazinyl)ethyl] phthalimide (IIa) (7.32 g, 0.02 mole) was refluxed with 20% HCl (60-70 ml) for 15 hrs. The solution was chilled and filtered to remove the precipitated phthalic acid. The filtrate was decolorized with charcoal and basified with 10% NaOH in cold. The separated oily base was taken up in solvent ether and the aqueous phase was repeatedly washed with ether. The combined ether extract was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Ether was evaporated. The residual oil was sufficiently pure for further use.

1-[2-(4-Phenyl-1-piperazinyl)ethyl]-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)piperidine-2,6-dione (IXa): The above oil, IIIa, (2.05 g, 0.01 mole) and 3-(4-methoxyphenyl) glutaric anhydride, VIII, (2.2 g, 0.01 mole) were refluxed in dry pyridine (40 ml) for 15 hrs. 10 ml of Ac₂O was added and the mixture was refluxed for further 5-6 hrs. The solution was concentrated *in vacuo*. Ethanol was then added to the residue and crude IXa was filtered. The product was crystallized from ethanol. m.p.: 174-75°; yield: 1.23 g (30%). (Found: C, 70.7; H, 7.21; N, 10.35%. C₂₄H₂₆N₄O₄ requires: C, 70.74; H, 7.17; N, 10.31%).

1-(2-Cyanoethyl)-4-phenylpiperazine (VIa): Phenylpiperazine (1.61 g, 0.01 mole) and acrylonitrile (0.8 g) were heated on a steam bath for 1 hr. The resulting crystalline mass was washed with water. The solid was crystallized from ethanol. m.p.: 71-72°; yield: 1.45 g (67%).

1-(3-Aminopropyl)-4-phenylpiperazine (VIIa): VIa was reduced by catalytic hydrogenation at R.T. under 50 psi pressure of H₂ with W-6 Raney-Ni as the catalyst. The solvent used was CH₃OH saturated with NH₃ gas.

1-[3-(4-Phenyl-1-piperazinyl)propyl]-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)piperidine-2,6-dione (Xa): It was prepared from VIIa and VIII following the procedure adopted for IX. m.p.: 164-65°; yield: 2.31 g (55%). (Found: C, 71.29; H, 7.37, N, 9.99%. C₂₅H₂₈N₄O₄ requires: C, 71.23; H, 7.41; N, 9.97%).

Pharmacology: All the compounds showed mild CNS depressant action in the preliminary screening. The compounds were injected i.p. in twin-80 suspension to Albino mice of Haffkin strain. The compounds possess LD₅₀ > 800 mg/kg. To characterize these compounds as psychosedatives, antagonism of the increased toxicity of amphetamine in mice was determined by the standard method¹⁴. Group of 10 mice, each weighing between 18-20 g, were injected various doses of the test compounds i.p. After 1 hr they were injected subcutaneously with 30 mg/kg of dl-amphetamine (LD₅₀). Deaths were recorded during 24 hrs. The dose required to protect 50% of the animals (ED₅₀, Table 1) was determined.

The activity increased with the length of the alkylene chain. Earlier reported compounds^{1a}, with (CH₂)₁ were the least active while, compounds with (CH₂)₃ chain, compounds X, were the most active. *Meta* and *para* substitution on the N-phenyl ring of the piperazine moiety reduced the activity. *Ortho* substitution increased the activity. *o*-Chloro substitution was the most favourable. Thus, Xf emerged out to be the most active drug in the present investigation and could be taken for further screening and for molecular manipulations.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Mr. S. M. Gupte for the pharmacological screening of the compounds. One of the authors (S.D.S.) is grateful to the UGC, New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

- I. GAGAUZOV, V. MATAFCHIEVA and D. DALEV, *Farmatsiya* (Sofia), 1968, 18, 7.
- I. GAGAUZOV and V. MATAFCHIEVA, *Farmatsiya* (Sofia), 1970, 20, 13.
- S. D. STANEVA, V. PETKOV and R. OVCHAROV, *Farmatsiya* (Sofia), 1970, 20, 43.
- C. L. C. CARRON, A. F. JULLIAN and B. M. RAIZON, *Fr. Demande*, 2,167,355, 1973; *Chem. Abs.*, 1974, 80, 37,016^m.
- T. C. SOMERS, *Nature*, 1956, 178, 996.
- YAO-HUA WU, K. R. SMITH, J. W. RAYBURN and J. W. KISSEL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, 12, 876.
- YAO-HUA WU and J. W. RAYBURN, *U. S. Patent*, 3,976,776, 1976; *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, 85, 192,766^d.
- F. A. EL-TELBANY, K. M. GHONEIN and M. KHALIFA, *Pharmazie*, 1977, 32, 22.
- O. L. MNDZHOYAN, L. M. PETROSYAN and N. E. AKOPYAN, *Arm. Khim. Zh.*, 1971, 24, 492; *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, 75, 129,485^a.
- C. B. POLLARD and L. G. MCDOWELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 2199.
- S. D. SAMANT and R. A. KULKARNI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 1002.
- S. D. SAMANT and R. A. KULKARNI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 819.
- S. HAYAO and R. N. SHUT, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 8415.
- J. H. BURN and B. HOBBS; *Arch int; Pharmacodyn. Ther.*, 1958, 113, 290.